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pinagpalapublishingservices@gmail.com

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The Evolution of Social Studies Education in the Philippines

ROSE L. AGLIAM

Teacher I

Schools Division of Tarlac Province

In the past few years, the Philippines has taken significant strides to revamp its social studies curriculum, aiming to foster active citizenship, critical thinking, and an appreciation for national history and heritage among its learners (Isip-Cumpas, 2024).

In 2024, a defining characteristic of social studies education in the Philippines was the renewed emphasis on local narratives and indigenous perspectives (Abad, 2024). This intent aligns with an increased consciousness and pride in Filipino identity and heritage. Integrating local stories and indigenous perspectives brought richness to learners' understanding of Filipino culture, imbued a sense of respect for diversity, and facilitated comprehensive historical understanding.

Moreover, understanding the significance of ASEAN integration has been a key focus area during this period. The education system acknowledged the need to prepare students to understand and participate in regional opportunities and challenges. Thus, the social studies curricula incorporated new content about Philippine relationships within the ASEAN community (Salazar-Clemeña, 2024).

An emerging trend was the increased inclusion of environmental education in the social studies curriculum (Magno, 2024). Environmental content emphasized the values of sustainability and stewardship, preparing young Filipinos to address environmental challenges and engage responsibly with their natural surroundings.

The adoption of innovative pedagogical strategies has also been prevalent. Project-based learning and inquiry-based instruction have been endorsed by social studies educators to foster critical thinking and active learning among students (Magtolis-Briones, 2024). These teaching methods encourage students to actively explore societal issues, engage in real-world problem solving, and develop skills required for democratic participation.

Furthermore, instructional technology has transformed the ways social studies is taught in the Philippines, offering new tools and resources for teaching and learning. The utilization of digital technologies provided opportunities for interactive learning, collaborative problem-solving, and exploration of diverse resources beyond textbooks (Aguas et al., 2024).

Despite these promising developments, challenges exist. These include the need for capacity-building for social studies teachers and fostering better alignment between curriculum objectives, instructional approaches, and assessment methods.

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Overall, the evolution of social studies education in the Philippines reflects a more equitable, relevant and dynamic approach, making continuous strides towards the goal of nurturing informed, active and globally-minded Filipino citizens.

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